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Uptake of *Ascaridia galli* extracellular vesicles by chicken immune cells varies according to worm sex and in vitro culture duration

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ABSTRACT

Ascaridia galli (*A. galli*), a parasitic roundworm that infects chickens poses an economic burden in poultry farming, as it causes ascariidiosis—a disease leading to reduced growth, lower egg production, and immunosuppression. Recently, interest has grown in the parasite's extracellular vesicles (EVs), as they modulate host immune responses and play a key role in host-pathogen interactions. This study aimed to optimize in vitro EV-production from *A. galli* and assess their uptake by chicken immune cells important for EV mediated host-pathogen communication. Adult worms were collected from infected chickens, sex-sorted, washed, and cultured in vitro. EVs were isolated at various time points using size exclusion chromatography and characterized. DiO-stained EVs were evaluated for uptake into chicken intestinal epithelial cells, macrophages, peripheral blood mononuclear cells and whole blood leukocytes using flow cytometry and confocal microscopy after 4 and 24 h incubation with the parasite derived vesicles. EV-uptake increased significantly from 4 h to 24 h across all tested cell types. Female-derived EVs collected after 24 h of worm culture gave rise to higher uptake than male-derived EVs. However, at the 40 h time point, male EVs gave rise to greater uptake, though overall EV internalization was reduced compared to the 24 h time point. Uptake efficiency varied depending on the EV collection time as well as the host cell type. These findings suggest that both the sex of the worm and the duration of culture influence EV uptake, with 24 h emerging as the optimal in vitro culture duration for production of *A. galli* derived EVs with potent biological functions. The sex-specific differences highlight potential functional diversity in EV mediated host-pathogen interactions, which need to be assessed in future studies.

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1. Introduction

Ascaridia galli (*A. galli*) is a common gastrointestinal nematode found among other avian species in laying hens, particularly in free-range systems, where it is a significant concern for the poultry production (Sharma et al., 2019). Heavy worm burdens can obstruct and damage the intestinal tract of the host, leading to reduced egg production and body weight in infected hens. Furthermore, *A. galli* infections can suppress the immune system, making hens more susceptible to secondary infections and altering nutrient utilization, which in severe cases can increase mortality within the flock (Hoglund et al., 2023; Shohana et al., 2023). Chickens

mount both cellular and humoral immune responses against *A. galli* infections within different parts of the gut mucosal immune system (Shohana et al. 2023). However, helminths have demonstrated complex interactions with the host immune system, with different strategies to evade and manipulate the host immune defenses (Drurey and Maizels, 2021; Hansen et al., 2019). Hence, no natural immunity develops in parasitized poultry as the nematodes modulate the avian host immune responses to avoid detection, allowing them to persist, continue their development and establish chronic infections (Hoglund et al., 2023). One of the key players in helminth immunomodulation are extracellular vesicles (EVs) that serve as vehicles for transferring signals between parasite and host cells, facilitating a sophisticated communication network that manipulates the host environment to favor parasite survival (Drurey and Maizels, 2021; Henthorn et al., 2023; Hoffmann et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2024). We have recently estab-

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lished that indeed *A. galli* produces EVs with potent immunomodulatory potential (Premathilaka et al., 2025a).

EVs are integrated in cell mediated host-pathogen communications via surface interactions or internalized by host cells through various pathways, including endocytosis, macropinocytosis, phagocytosis, or membrane fusion (Abels and Breakefield, 2016). Recipient cells exhibit diversity in their preferences for the uptake of exosomes (Ofir-Birin et al., 2018). NK cells, for example, demonstrate a higher capacity to internalize exosomes originating from themselves and from cell lines derived from bone marrow (Sabatke et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). In contrast, epithelial cell lines show a greater ability to take up exosomes derived from other epithelial cells (Wang et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2024). The recipient cell type influences EV uptake, regardless of the donor cell type, emphasizing the importance of considering the specific characteristics of recipient cells in understanding intercellular communication through EVs (Abels and Breakefield, 2016; Sabatke et al., 2024). The uptake of nematode derived EVs by immune cells is not fully understood (Drurey and Maizels 2021; Hoffmann et al. 2020). Studies about the uptake of helminth derived EVs are still scarce and research has focused on uptake in mammalian immune cells. Exosome-like vesicles from *Echinococcus granulosus* showed that they can be internalized by host dendritic cells and carry immunoregulatory proteins (Nicolao et al., 2019). In other parasites, like *Leishmania* spp. (Ferreira et al., 2022) and *Plasmodium* spp. (Ben Ami Pilo et al., 2022; Khawawisetsut et al., 2023) the pathogen-derived exosomes are vehicles for their protein secretion and their uptake is evident in host monocytes. In general, monocytes are known to take up high amounts of EVs, as they express high levels of class A type I/II (CD204) and class B (CD36) phagocytic receptors (O'Dea et al., 2020). Furthermore, neutrophils are reported to be rapid responders for EV uptake (Rossaint et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2023). However, lymphocytes, which are also known to internalize parasite EVs, take them up at a lesser extent, as they use a receptor mediated uptake mechanism, which is more selective (Nicolao et al., 2019). Labeling EVs allows for better tracking their distribution, localization, and uptake in recipient cells, with lipophilic fluorescent dyes being a popular choice for tracking EV internalization by microscopy (Simonsen, 2019; Thery et al., 2018). However, this technique has one disadvantage, as only EV clusters can be visualized, and not single EVs. This makes it valuable to use supplementary strategies to evaluate EV uptake with different visualization techniques to quantify, visualize and validate them (Simonsen, 2019). Although chicken nematodes are increasingly prevalent in Europe and new therapeutic strategies are needed, research on nematode-derived EVs in poultry host cells remains largely unexplored. Herein we assessed and improved the enrichment of EVs from *A. galli* from in vitro cultivation systems and show differences in EV shedding of male and female worms. Furthermore, we addressed *A. galli* derived EV-uptake in different host immune cell types. Firstly, a chicken intestinal epithelial cell line was used to assess EV uptake in vitro, to substantiate if uptake is possible directly in the gut of the chicken in vivo situation during the early host-pathogen communications. Next, we addressed the in vitro uptake of *A. galli* EVs in different avian immune cell subsets, which may have direct function in the immune response in vivo. This information will help to better understand the mechanism by which *A. galli* modulates the host immune system, as well as the role of *A. galli* EVs as immunomodulatory agents.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Collection and preparation of *A. galli* worms

Adult *A. galli* worms were collected from the intestines of twenty hens obtained from a commercial organic breeder in Den-

mark. Following dissection of the small intestine, the worms were immediately transferred into 0.9 % NaCl solution. Live worms were maintained at room temperature during transport to the laboratory, where they were washed thoroughly three times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at room temperature. Subsequently, the worms were separated by sex into male and female groups. Following sexing, the worms were measured and categorized by length into small, medium, and large size groups (Table 1). They were then washed three times with EV-free RPMI 1640 culture medium (Gibco, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA, RPMI supplemented with vesicle-depleted fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA (cat. no. BE12-115F/U1, Lonza))). The worms were transferred to T75 culture flasks at a density of 20 worms per 30 mL of EV-free RPMI. RPMI was selected as the culture medium due to previously reported superior maintenance of worm viability compared to alternative media (Ritu et al., 2024). To determine the optimal culture length for EV-yield during different time points, experiments were conducted in triplicate. Spent medium including EVs were collected at defined intervals (18 h, 24 h, 40 h, 48 h) and stored at -80°C until further processing and EV enrichment. The incubation timepoints were defined from the worms being put into medium until the time the medium was harvested.

2.2. EV enrichment

EVs were enriched by following the protocols described in previous studies with minor modifications (Premathilaka et al., 2025a; Premathilaka et al., 2025b; Welsh et al., 2024; White et al., 2023). In brief, spent medium was centrifuged at 300g for 10 min at 4°C to remove the nematode eggs. After that three successive centrifugation steps (400g, 4000g, and 10,000g for 10 min) were performed to remove cells and cell debris. The collected supernatant was filtered through a polyethersulfone 0.45 μm filter (Minisart syringe filter, Gottingen, Germany) and concentrated to 500 μL with Amicon Ultra-15 centrifugal filter devices (10 kDa cutoff, MerckMillipore, Darmstadt, Germany). The EVs were enriched from the concentrated supernatant using size exclusion chromatography (SEC) in a cross-linked 4 % agarose matrix of 90 μm beads (Sepharose 4 Fast Flow, GE HealthCare Bio-Sciences AB, Uppsala, Sweden) in a 10 cm gravity column calibrated with PBS. The eluate was collected into 20 fractions, each containing 500 μL . The fractions 5 to 7 with high EV numbers and negligible protein contamination were selected based on the nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) data and Bradford assay. All fractions were concentrated to 500 μL .

2.3. EV characterization

2.3.1. Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA)

Concentrations and sizes of nanoparticles in each fraction were measured with NTA ZetaView[®] (PMX 110V3.0 instrument by Particle Metrix GmbH, Inning am Ammersee, Germany, software version 8.05.14 SP7) coupled with ZetaView NTA software for data analysis (Premathilaka et al., 2025b). The operating instructions of the manufacturer were followed as described in the literature. The auto-alignment of the instrument was performed using 100 nm polystyrene particle size standards (Applied Microspheres B.V., Leusden, Netherlands). The samples were measured in the scatter mode for estimation of the total particle concentration and size profiles using the following settings: camera sensitivity 85, shutter 70, frame rate 30 frames per second (fps), number of cycles 3, and number of frames 11.

2.3.2. Protein quantification

Bradford Assay (Pierce[™] Bradford Protein Assay Kit, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) was used to determine the

Table 1
Average sizes of worms used for time point experiments and categories used for sizing of worms.

	18 h	24 h	40 h	48 h
Female	6.66 ± 1.04 Large: 6.9–8 cm Medium: 5.7–6.8 cm Small: 4.5–5.6 cm	6.50 ± 1.09	5.78 ± 1.02	6.41 ± 1.26
Male	4.59 ± 0.73 Large: 4.9–6 cm Medium: 3.7–4.8 cm Small: 2.5–3.6 cm,	3.94 ± 0.71	4.33 ± 0.72	3.94 ± 1.11

protein concentration of eluted fractions. Dilution series of the standard bovine serum albumin (BSA) solution (2 mg/mL, Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA) were prepared (1.4, 1.0, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.125 mg/mL). PBS was used as a negative control. Subsequently, three replicates of each sample, standards, and negative control of 5 µL were added to a 96-well microplate. Following this, 95 µL of Bradford Reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA) was added to each well. The microplate was covered with aluminum foil and kept on a shaker for 30 s for homogenous mixing. Then, the microplate was incubated at room temperature for 15–30 min. At last, the absorbance of the standards and the samples were measured with a spectrophotometer (Ledetect 96 Microplate Reader; Biomed Dr. Wieser GmbH, Salzburg, Austria) at 620 nm wavelength and the protein concentrations of each of the fractions were calculated (Premathilaka et al., 2025b).

2.3.3. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Morphological evaluation of EVs were carried out by employing TEM (Premathilaka et al., 2025b). First, 20 µL of EV suspension was placed on formvar/carbon-coated 200 mesh grids (Agar Scientific, Stansted, UK). The EVs were allowed to absorb on the grid for 20 min. Afterward, the same grids were incubated with 2 % uranyl acetate (Polysciences, Warrington, PA, USA) for 5 min and air-dried to obtain contrasted images of EVs. The EVs were visualized using JEM 1400 TEM (JEOL Ltd. Tokyo, Japan, with Morada TEM CCD camera, Olympus, Hamburg, Germany) at 80 kV. The digital images of EV were captured using a numeric camera (Morada TEM CCD camera, Olympus, Hamburg, Germany).

2.4. Preparation of host cells

2.4.1. Cultivation of 8E11 cells

The chicken intestinal epithelial cell line 8E11 was cultured under standard conditions with $1-2 \times 10^6$ cells placed in a T75 culture flask and 15 mL of culture medium. 8E11 cells were maintained in DMEM/F12 culture medium (Gibco, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA) supplemented with 10 % FBS (Gibco, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA (cat. no. BE12-115F/U1, Lonza)), 1 % penicillin–streptomycin (Gibco, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA), and incubated at 41 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂. Media were replaced every 2–3 days or as required based on cell density. For use in uptake assays cells were sown into plates at a concentration of 80,000 cells per 100 µL for each well in DMEM culture medium supplemented with 10 % FBS but without any antibiotics.

2.4.2. Cultivation of HD11 cells

The chicken macrophage-like cell line HD11 was cultured under standard conditions with $1-2 \times 10^6$ cells placed in a T75 culture flask and 10 mL of culture medium. HD11 cells were maintained in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10 % FBS, 1 % penicillin–streptomycin and incubated at 41 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂. Media were replaced every 2–3 days

or as required based on cell density. For use in uptake assays cells were sown into plates at a concentration of 80,000 cells per 100 µL for each well in RPMI culture medium supplemented with 10 % FBS but without any antibiotics.

2.4.3. Whole blood

Blood samples were obtained from the jugular vein and collected into Vacuette® tubes coated with 18 IU/ml Sodium Heparin (Greiner Bio-One, cat. no. 454030) of three adult hens from the AU inbred line 21 with the MHC haplotype B19. The whole blood was diluted 1:100 with RPMI and 0.125 µl/ml of CD45-PerCP-Cy5.5 antibody (clone UM16-6, Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc., CA, USA) was added before uptake studies. Fluorochrome conjugation of unlabelled anti-CD45 with PerCP-Cy5.5 was performed beforehand using Lightning-Link® PerCP/Cy5.5® Conjugation Kit (Innova Bioscience Ltd., UK) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.4.4. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC)

Blood samples were obtained from the jugular vein as described above. Four ml of peripheral blood from each animal were diluted with an equal amount of PBS. Diluted blood was carefully layered onto Ficoll-Paque® reagent (Cytiva, Uppsala, SE, lot no: 10296932) in two 15 ml polypropylene tubes which were centrifuged at 400g for 25 min 20 °C (acceleration 5, brake 1). Following centrifugation, the interphase and everything above it was transferred to a new 15 ml tube containing 10 ml of PBS, centrifuged at 300g for 10 min followed by two additional washes with PBS. After discarding the supernatant, cells were resuspended in RPMI-1640 supplemented with 10 % FBS at a concentration of 2×10^7 cells/ml for uptake assays.

2.5. Staining of EVs and assessing their scatter profiles by flow cytometry

EVs of fractions 5–7 were pooled and stained using DiO (FAST DiO, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA) at a final concentration of 40 µM for 20 min at room temperature keeping the sample protected from light, under constant shaking. To remove the excess dye, ultracentrifugation was performed. To assess the scatter properties of the DiO stained EVs the CytoFLEX Nano small particle flow cytometer equipped with four lasers (405 nm, 488 nm, 561 nm, and 638 nm) (Beckman Coulter, Indianapolis, US). Biological controls, buffer only, buffer + reagent, and unstained EV-controls were implemented to ensure correct identification of DiO positive EVs. Prior to analysis by nano-flow cytometry, all samples were passed through a 0.22 µm PES syringe filter (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) to remove large particles and aggregates. Samples were then pre-diluted using a low-background PBS buffer (L0615, Biowest, Nuaille, Pays de la Loire, France) to minimize background noise and ensure that the event rate during acquisition remained below 3000 events per second. To exclude the contributing signal from the buffer, inclusion gates were set within the VSSC1 signal and

swarming events were excluded by setting VSSC1 width versus VSSC1.

2.6. Uptake assays, flow cytometry

2.6.1. Cell lines

To evaluate the uptake of fluorescently labeled EVs, cells were incubated with EVs at 541 °C for either 4 h or 24 h. In total 80,000 HD11 or 8E11 cells in 100 µl culture medium per well were allowed to rest overnight before adding 50 µl of DiO stained EVs (1:1250). After incubation, cells were washed thoroughly with PBS to remove unbound EVs. Adherent 8E11 or HD11 cells were detached using 200 µl pre-warmed 5 mM EDTA per well (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Cells were incubated at 41 °C for approximately 5 min until detachment was observed whereafter cells were transferred to round bottom plates (Nunc™, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), centrifuged at 200g for 5 min whereafter the supernatant was flicked out and cells were gently resuspended in 100 µl PBS before flow cytometry acquisition.

2.6.2. Whole blood

In each well 50 µl of stained EVs were added (concentration of 1:1250) to 50 µl of diluted whole blood in non-stick 96-well plates (Nunc™, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and incubated for 4 h at 5 % CO₂ and 41 °C. After incubation, cells were fixed with a final concentration of paraformaldehyde (PFA) of 1 % kept overnight at 4 °C. The sample was acquired on a BD FACS Celesta (BD Biosciences, San Jose, USA) equipped with 488 nm blue, 633 nm red, and 405 nm violet lasers, with data analyzed using the Diva™ v9.0 (BD Bioscience, San Jose, CA, USA) software. Every biological replicate was repeated in three technical triplicates.

2.6.3. PBMC

The isolated PBMCs were added at a concentration of 1×10^6 cells in 50 µl per well in a 96-well plate. 50 µl of fluorescent EVs (conc 1:1250) were added to the cells and incubated for 4 h and 24 h respectively, 5 % CO₂, 41 °C. Afterwards, incubation plates were centrifuged at 600g for 5 min and the supernatant was flicked out. Cells were stained with fluorescent antibodies in 100 µl PBS for 15 min at room temperature in the dark. The staining panel included: CD41/61-PE (clone 11C3, Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc., CA, USA); Kul-01-A647 (clone KUL01, Southern Biotech, AL, USA); CD45-PerCPCy5.5 (clone UM-16, Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc., CA, USA); CD3-A700 (clone CT3, SouthernBiotech, AL, USA); BU-1-pBlue (clone AV20, SouthernBiotech, AL, USA). Furthermore, the fixable LIVE/DEAD® near-IR fluorescent amine reactive dye (Invitrogen-Molecular Probes, Eugene, USA) was included as viability dye. Optimal antibody concentrations were determined beforehand and fluorescence minus one (FMO) controls were included. Cells were washed twice with FACs buffer (0.2 % BSA, 0.2 % sodium azide, Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA, 0.05 % normal horse serum, Gibco, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA) by centrifugation at 600g for 5 min. After the last centrifugation step the stained cells were resuspended in 100 µl of FACs buffer. The sample was acquired on a BD FACS Celesta (BD Biosciences, San Jose, USA) equipped with 488 nm blue, 633 nm red, and 405 nm violet lasers. Every biological replicate was repeated in three technical triplicates.

2.7. Uptake assays, confocal microscopy

For visualization of EV uptake, 8E11 and HD11 cells were seeded at a density of 20,000 cells per well onto poly-L-lysine-coated chamber slides and allowed to adhere and grow for at least 24 h. DiO-labeled EVs were added to the cells and incubated for 4 h

and 24 h at 41 °C and 5 % CO₂. A total of 100 µl of stained EV suspension at a concentration of (1:1250) was applied per well. A control group exposed to unstained EVs was included for all time points. Following incubation, cells were washed three times with PBS to remove unbound EVs. Cells were then fixed in 4 % PFA for 15 min at room temperature, followed by permeabilization with 0.25 % Triton X-100 for 10 min. To reduce nonspecific binding, cells were blocked with 4 % BSA for 30 min at room temperature. After blocking, cells were washed three times with PBS and stained with phalloidin for 10 min to label cell actin filaments. Following another three PBS washes, slides were mounted using Fluoromount-G containing DAPI to counterstain nuclei. Slides were stored protected from light until imaging. Image acquisition and analyses were performed at the Bioimaging Core Facility, Health, Aarhus University, Denmark on a LSM 900 laser scanning confocal with a ZEN 3.5 system (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) and pictures were taken with the Axiocam 305 mono camera system (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany).

2.8. Statistical analysis

Flow cytometry plots were generated in Flow Jo v.11 (Ashland, OR, USA) or Diva™ v9.0 (San Jose, CA, USA) and the Nano Flow data in CytExpert nano (v. 1.1.0.6, Beckman Coulter, Souzhou, China) and intensities of confocal microscopy was analyzed in ZEN.blue 3.11 (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany). All further data was processed in Graph Pad Prism 10.5.0 (Boston, MA, USA) and an ANOVA was performed. Statistical significance was set at * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

2.9. Data accessibility

All data supporting the findings of this study are available in Mendely Data under the accession number <https://doi.org/10.17632/jm7kc7ss3x.1>. This includes raw data, a detailed protocol and analysis files used for generating the results presented in this manuscript. Additional supporting materials and protocols are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

3. Results

3.1. Kinetics of *A. galli* shedding

To determine ways to obtain the highest amount of EVs shed by *A. galli* several kinetics experiments were conducted. First the cleaned and sexed worms were split into groups in accordance with their size. Both in female and male worms the medium size (females: 5.7–6.8 cm, males: 3.7–4.8 cm) shed the most particles per mL indicating an effect of life stage on EV production (Fig. 1A). The amount of EVs shed by *A. galli* was relatively stable in each repetition, however we did observe some differences between the ideal worm culture length, in which *A. galli* females or males shed the highest amount of EVs. While for female worms the highest average particle yield was determined after 24 h of culture, with no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in the particle yield to a 48 h incubation period (Fig. 1B), male worms numerically shed the highest amount of EVs after 40 h of culture (Fig. 1C). However, there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between the time-points in the male particle yield (Fig. 1C). Also, no morphological differences between the different EV fractions were identified (Fig. 1D and E). After SEC, EVs were mainly found in fractions 5, 6, 7 and 8 from *A. galli* females, with the highest EV yield in fraction 6 (Fig. 1F). From male worms the EV yield in every fraction was significantly lower ($P < 0.01$). Furthermore, no EVs were found in fraction 8 of *A. galli* males (Fig. 1G). The particles sizes of EVs shed by the different worm sexes did not differ. Most of the particles were

Fig. 1. Kinetics and characterization EV shedding by *A. galli*. A: EV yield from size-separated male and female worms. B: Time-course of EV shedding by female worms by different culture lengths. C: Time-course of EV shedding by female worms by different culture lengths. D: Transmission electron microscopy of EVs, scalebar: 200 μ m. E: Transmission electron microscopy of EVs, scalebar: 200 μ m. F: EV distribution across density gradient fractions from female worms. Violet shows the EV concentration during a 24 h incubation. Pink shows the EV concentration during a 40 h incubation. G: EV distribution across density gradient fractions from male worms. Darkblue shows the EV concentration during a 24 h incubation. Light blue shows the EV concentration during a 40 h incubation. H: Size distribution profiles of EVs from female worms. I: Size distribution profiles of EVs from male worms. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

between 100 and 200 nm in size (Fig. 1H and I). The average number of EVs showed that medium size worms of both sexes shed the most EVs (Table 2).

The *A. galli* derived EVs were further characterized using flow cytometry to assess light scattering of fluorescent stained vesicles (Fig. 2). It is possible to distinguish vesicle subpopulations based on size, granularity, and membrane labeling with DiO. In the current experiment, it was evident from the whole population of vesicles that only approximately 30 % were labeled with DiO. However, the DiO intensity (B531) appeared similar between the sexes and all timepoints (Fig. 2A). Interestingly, both male and female EVs exhibited a broad range of size and complexity, as seen from the wide scatter distributions. Within the DiO+ EV population two distinct subsets were identified by YSSC (Yellow side scatter) versus

Table 2

Average number of EVs shed by worms of different sizes and sex (in EVs per individual worm).

	Female	Male
Large	8.58×10^5	8.81×10^5
Medium	3.82×10^6	3.11×10^6
Small	1.94×10^6	4.80×10^5

VSSC1 (violet side scatter 1) plots – one of which showing increased YSSC (YSSC^{hi} population) (Fig. 2A). Interestingly, the YSSC^{hi} population was more pronounced in male than in female cultures after 24 h of culture (around 48 % versus 24 % respectively) whereas all 40 h cultures showed a frequency of around 30 % for both male and female (Fig. 2B).

Fig. 2. Representative flow cytometry plots of EVs derived from male and female *A. galli*. A: Left DiO fluorescence (B531) versus VSSC-1 plots – right shown only for DiO positive cells: YSSC versus VSSC-1 plots. B: YSSC versus VSSC-1 plots shown for DiO stained EVs from male and female cultures of 24 h or 40 h length. The YSSC hi population is shown in blue. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.2. Sex differences in uptake of *A. galli* EVs in host cells

Uptake of DiO stained *A. galli* derived EVs were studied in the chicken intestinal epithelial cell line 8E11 (Fig. 3). Flow cytometry was used to assess the frequency of DiO+ cells and uptake differences were identified when comparing EVs enriched from different worm sexes at different culture lengths. Following a 4 h uptake incubation of host cells with EVs from female and male *A. galli* cultures (collected at 24 h and 40 h), minimal EV uptake was observed (Fig. 3A). After a 24 h uptake incubation period, a marked increase in EV uptake was observed, particularly for EVs derived from female worms collected after 24 h of culture, reaching up to around 23 % uptake in the epithelial cells (Fig. 3B). Interestingly, the cell uptake frequency when using 24 h male culture EVs were significantly lower than when using 24 h female EVs. However, for EVs from 40 h cultures the male derived cell uptake frequency was higher than the female frequency (Fig. 3B). The intensity of EVs taken up by 10 randomly selected representative 8E11 cells in confocal microscopy was evaluated as an indication of the amounts of EVs taken up per positive cell. No sex differences were observed in the 24 h culture EVs when using 4 h cell uptake incubation (Fig. 3C) or 24 h cell uptake incubation (Fig. 3D). The host cell uptake of EVs derived from 40 h worm cultures varied between the two uptake incubation lengths. After 4 h of incubation, significantly more ($P < 0.001$) EVs were taken up per host cell if they were male derived as compared to female derived (Fig. 3C). Moreover, after 24 h incubation, significantly more EVs ($P < 0.001$) were taken up per host cell if they were female derived as compared to male derived (Fig. 3D).

All controls of cells incubated with unstained EVs—regardless of the worm incubation time—did not exhibit any detectable signal in the confocal microscopy assay (Fig. 3E, F, K, L), confirming that the observed fluorescence was specific to DiO labeling and EV uptake. As expected from the flow cytometry data only low numbers of vis-

ible DiO-positive EVs after a 4 h incubation period was detected, regardless of whether the EVs were derived from female or male worms (Fig. 3G, I, M, O). In contrast, when the uptake incubation period was extended to 24 h, the number of DiO+ host cells increased markedly (Fig. 3H, J, N, P). The EVs appeared as more prominent clumps within the cells, indicating greater uptake as reflected by the DiO intensity readings. Overall, a consistent increase in EV signal intensity was observed when comparing the 4 h to the 24 h cell incubation period across all worm incubation timepoints.

Uptake of DiO stained *A. galli* derived EVs were also studied in the chicken macrophage-like cell line HD11 (Fig. 4). Flow cytometry was used to assess the frequency of DiO+ cells, and no uptake differences were identified when comparing EVs enriched from different worm sexes at different culture lengths after a 4 h uptake incubation period with host cells (Fig. 4A). After a 24 h uptake incubation period, a marked increase in EV uptake was observed for EVs derived from female worms collected after 24 h of culture, just as we observed in the epithelial cells. Interestingly, the cell uptake frequency when using 24 h male culture EVs were significantly lower ($P < 0.001$) than when using 24 h female EVs. However, for EVs from 40 h cultures the male derived cell uptake frequency was higher than the female frequency (Fig. 4B).

The intensity of EVs taken up by 10 randomly selected representative HD11 cells in confocal microscopy was evaluated as an indication of the amounts of EVs taken up per positive cell. No sex differences were observed when using 4 h cell uptake incubation (Fig. 4C) or when using 24 h uptake incubation (Fig. 4D). The intensity in cells exposed to female EVs from 24 h and 40 h cultures were numerically higher, but no statistical differences were identified ($P > 0.05$).

No DiO+ signal was detected in control groups treated with unstained EVs (Fig. 4E, F, K, L). As expected from the flow cytometry data only low numbers of visible DiO-positive EVs after a 4 h

Fig. 3. Uptake of *A. galli*-derived EVs by 8E11 cells after different incubation periods. A: 4 h incubation with DiO stained EVs and frequency of DiO+ cells assessed by flow cytometry. B: 24 h incubation with DiO stained EVs and frequency of DiO+ cells assessed by flow cytometry. C: Intensity of parasite EVs taken up by 8E11 host cells shown with confocal microscopy during a 4 h incubation. D: Intensity of parasite EVs taken up by 8E11 host cells shown with confocal microscopy during a 24 h incubation. E: 4 h incubation with unstained EVs from *A. galli*. F: 24 h incubation with unstained EVs from *A. galli*. G: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h female *A. galli*. H: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h female *A. galli*. I: 4 h incubation with unstained EVs from 40 h female *A. galli*. J: 24 h incubation with unstained EVs from 40 h female *A. galli*. K: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 40 h female *A. galli*. L: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 40 h female *A. galli*. M: 4 h incubation with unstained EVs from 24 h male *A. galli*. N: 24 h incubation with unstained EVs from 24 h male *A. galli*. O: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h male *A. galli*. P: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h male *A. galli*. All confocal pictures are shown in pairs where the left shows fully stained samples and the right shows only the DiO fluorescence from the EVs. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Fig. 4. Uptake of *A. galli*-derived EVs by HD11 cells after different incubation periods. A: 4 h incubation with DiO stained EVs and frequency of DiO+ cells assessed by flow cytometry. B: 24 h incubation with DiO stained EVs and frequency of DiO+ cells assessed by flow cytometry. C: Intensity of parasite EVs taken up by HD11 host cells shown with confocal microscopy during a 4 h incubation. D: Intensity of parasite EVs taken up by HD11 host cells shown with confocal microscopy during a 24 h incubation. E: 4 h incubation with unstained EVs from *A. galli*. F: 24 h incubation with unstained EVs from *A. galli*. G: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h female *A. galli*. H: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h female *A. galli*. I: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h male *A. galli*. J: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 24 h male *A. galli*. K: 4 h incubation with unstained EVs from *A. galli*. L: 24 h incubation with unstained EVs from *A. galli*. M: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 40 h female *A. galli*. N: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 40 h female *A. galli*. O: 4 h incubation with stained EVs from 40 h male *A. galli*. P: 24 h incubation with stained EVs from 40 h male *A. galli*. All confocal pictures are shown in pairs where the left shows fully stained samples and the right shows only the DiO fluorescence from the EVs. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

incubation period was detected, regardless of whether the EVs were derived from female or male worms (Fig. 4G, I, M, O). However, when the incubation period was extended to 24 h, a marked increase in EV uptake was observed in HD11 cells for all EV samples (Fig. 4H, J, N, P). EVs appeared as larger and more distinct fluorescent clusters, indicating more extensive internalization. These findings demonstrate enhanced uptake following 24 h exposure compared to the 4 h incubation. This pattern was consistent across EVs from different worm incubation timepoints and sexes.

3.2.1. Uptake of *A. galli* EVs in chicken peripheral blood cells

Flow cytometry analysis was performed to assess the uptake of EVs by different whole blood cell populations, including heterophils, monocytes, lymphocytes, and thrombocytes during a 4 h incubation period. The control samples with no added EVs were used to set negative gates (Fig. 5A–D). Diluted blood incubated with DiO stained EVs showed varying uptake of *A. galli* derived EVs in different cell subsets (Fig. 5E–H). Heterophils showed moderate uptake of EVs, with the uptake of female-derived EVs being significantly higher, than all other groups with the 24 h culture batch inducing a significantly greater uptake ($P < 0.001$) compared to later time points in general. Male-derived EVs showed a significantly higher uptake ($P < 0.001$) for EVs derived from 40 h cultures as compared to female-derived EVs from same culture length (Fig. 5I). Of all tested cell subsets, monocytes showed the highest frequency of EV positive cell, with significant differences ($P < 0.001$) between EVs of male and female worms derived both from 24 h incubation and 40 h incubated worms (Fig. 5J). In contrast to 24 h culture worms, the vesicles of male worms, which were incubated for 40 h were taken up at higher frequencies than female derived vesicles (Fig. 5J). For lymphocytes (Fig. 5K), EVs derived from female worms, which were incubated for 24 h, were taken up better than those derived from males at the same time point. The opposed picture was shown for worms from 40 h cultures. Thrombocytes showed (Fig. 5L) no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) at the 40 h timepoint, however, EVs derived from female worms, which were incubated for 24 h, were taken up significantly better ($P < 0.001$) than those derived of males at the same time point.

The EV uptake studies were repeated in PBMCs where uptake was assessed in additional cell subsets like B and T cells (Fig. 6A–D). As opposed to the whole blood assay it was possible to assess uptake both after 4 and 24 h in the PBMC cultures. In all PBMC subsets examined, the uptake of EVs during a 24 h incubation period was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) than during 4 h incubation (Fig. 6E, H, I, K).

Monocytes, as shown in the whole blood assay, exhibited the highest frequency of EV+ cells, with differences between female-derived EVs and male-derived EVs after both 4 h and 24 h uptake incubation (Fig. 6E). Interestingly, the EVs derived from male *A. galli* cultured for 24 h gave rise to unexpectedly high frequencies of EV positive monocytes after incubation of only 4 h. (Fig. 6E). Furthermore, confocal microscopy confirmed the uptake of *A. galli* derived EVs by monocytes, with EVs being closely associated with the nucleus of the host cells (Fig. 6F). A similar association of EVs close to the nucleus was also shown for thrombocytes (Fig. 6G). Thrombocytes displayed moderate to low frequencies of EV+ cells. Significant differences ($P < 0.001$) between sexes could be shown between EVs derived from 24 h cultures incubated with PBMCs for 4 h, and to a lesser extent between the sexes after 24 h of PBMC incubation when 40 h culture EVs were used (Fig. 6H).

B cells and T cells overall exhibited low uptake of *A. galli*-derived EVs, however, a closer examination revealed subtle yet statistically significant patterns ($P < 0.001$) that emphasize the nuanced responsiveness of these lymphocyte subsets. B cells incubated with EVs derived from female *A. galli* cultured for 24 h dis-

played a modest but significantly elevated ($P < 0.001$) frequency of EV+ cells compared to male-derived EV conditions. For 40 h worm cultures male EVs were taken up by higher frequencies of cells than female-derived EVs (Fig. 6I). Lymphocytes, including B cells and T cells could not be differentiated with confocal microscopy during morphological examinations. Nuclei of lymphocytes stuck close together and *A. galli*-derived EVs were visible in clumps around the host cell nuclei (Fig. 6J).

T cell populations isolated from PBMCs followed a similar trend showing a very low EV uptake frequency. Female EVs from 24 h cultures induced significantly greater EV uptake than male EVs even after 4 h of uptake. Although the magnitude of uptake was lower compared to monocytes or thrombocytes, the statistically significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in EV+ T cells upon extended exposure underscores a biologically relevant interaction (Fig. 6K).

4. Discussion

In the context of EV-mediated host–pathogen interactions, EVs can either interact with surface receptors and ligands on target cells or be internalized through active uptake mechanisms. In the present study, we primarily focused on interactions mediated by EV uptake. EV uptake over 24 h was significantly higher than after 4 h for both male- and female-derived EVs across all tested host cell lines, but the uptake levels varied depending on the worm culture time in both in vitro cultured host cells and peripheral blood leukocytes. The observed sex-related differences may suggest functional variation (Mondal et al., 2016; Vanhamme et al., 2020). Given that both sexes coexist in the host, future studies should focus on EVs from mixed-sex cultures to better reflect in vivo conditions, as shown in other nematode species (Druey and Maizels, 2021; Hansen et al., 2019; White et al., 2023). Macrophage cell lines are widely used in EV uptake studies due to their capacity to internalize EVs through multiple mechanisms throughout all animal kingdoms (Pham et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2022). However, not all mechanisms have been proven for the uptake of parasite derived EVs within the host cell (Abels and Breakefield, 2016; Sabatke et al., 2024). Mammalian macrophages potentially take up parasite derived EVs via endocytosis, which involves the host cells endocytic pathway and phagocytosis, which is normally used for larger particles (Sabatke et al., 2024). This uptake by macrophages can modulate the mammalian immune response and affect the pathogenesis of infections (Qadeer et al., 2024; Sabatke et al., 2024). Specifically, there are examples of EV cargo playing a key role in shaping macrophage responses as shown for EVs from *Trypanosoma brucei rhodesiense* that can deliver the serum resistance-associated protein SRA, aiding immune evasion (Rodrigues et al., 2025; Torrecilhas et al., 2020).

Female worms, likely prioritizing early immune modulation to facilitate reproduction, may release EVs earlier due to higher initial metabolic and secretory activity. In contrast, males may exhibit delayed EV release aligned with their distinct roles in host interaction (Qadeer et al., 2024). Beyond acting as a physical barrier, gut epithelial cells actively contribute to immune surveillance and modulation, participating in antigen presentation and cytokine signaling (Shohana et al., 2023). The uptake of parasite-derived EVs by intestinal epithelial cells suggests a potential route for *A. galli* to influence host immunity at the gut interface early in infection. This interaction may be critical for shaping the local immune environment and facilitating parasite survival and reproduction (Kunisawa and Kiyono, 2013).

Although the uptake of EVs by chicken immune cells has not earlier been investigated, this represents a relevant area for future research, as chickens comprise the largest population of land animals raised for food globally (Govoni et al., 2021; Sharma et al.,

Fig. 5. Uptake of parasite-derived EVs by chicken whole blood cell populations with representative flow cytometry plots. A: uptake of unstained EV control in heterophils. B: uptake of unstained EV control in monocytes. C: uptake of unstained EV control in lymphocytes. D: uptake of unstained EV control in thrombocytes. E: uptake of DiO+ EVs in heterophils. F: uptake of DiO+ EVs in monocytes. G: uptake of DiO+ EVs in lymphocytes. H: uptake of DiO+ EVs in thrombocytes. I: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of heterophils, that took up DiO+ EVs. J: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of monocytes, that took up DiO+ EVs. K: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of lymphocytes, that took up DiO+ EVs. L: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of thrombocytes, that took up DiO+ EVs. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

2019). This prominence makes them a valuable model for both basic EV research and the development of novel therapeutic strategies. Existing studies in avian species indicate that peripheral blood leukocytes, particularly thrombocytes, are capable of both releasing and potentially internalizing host-derived EVs, highlighting their potential involvement in EV-mediated communication (Sugimoto et al., 2023). We showed uptake of *A. galli*-derived EVs in chicken monocytes, thrombocytes, lymphocytes and heterophils. Monocytes play a central role in host-pathogen interactions and have been shown to actively internalize EVs, leading to significant transcriptomic and functional changes in mammals (Khowawisetsut et al., 2023; O'Dea et al., 2020). For instance, EVs derived from *Plasmodium falciparum*-infected red blood cells from humans deliver virulence factors such as PfEMP1 to monocytes, inducing marked shifts in gene expression and immune activation (Ben Ami Pilo et al., 2022). Similarly, EVs can transport pathogenic molecules that trigger host cell responses and modulate the course of infection (Drurey and Maizels, 2021; Hoffmann et al., 2020; Marcilla et al., 2014). Experimental techniques such as flow cytometry and microscopy have been widely employed to assess EV uptake in monocytes, offering both quantitative and visual confirmation of internalization (White et al., 2023). Additional methods,

including NTA and qPCR, further support the detection and analysis of EV cargo within recipient cells (Welsh et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). Studies have also highlighted the rapid uptake kinetics of parasite-derived EVs—over 90 % of monocytes internalize *P. falciparum* EVs within 10 min of exposure—although no cytotoxic effects are observed up to 72 h post-uptake (Ben Ami Pilo et al., 2022; Ofir-Birin et al., 2018). Moreover, EV internalization has been shown to enhance the secretion of key cytokines such as IL-6 and MMP-9, factors involved in inflammation and tissue remodeling, which may mirror pre-metastatic niche formation seen in cancer models (Sheridan et al., 2024) and similar signaling between embryo and maternal tract (Dissanayake et al., 2024; Fazeli and Godakumara, 2024). These findings underscore the immunomodulatory potential of parasite-derived EVs and support the likelihood of *A. galli* EV uptake by monocytes, positioning them as important targets for further investigation in host-parasite EV communication.

Other immune cells such as thrombocytes and lymphocytes are increasingly recognized as active participants in host-pathogen interactions involving EVs (Marcilla et al., 2014; Schorey et al., 2015). In avian species, thrombocytes—functional equivalents of mammalian platelets—have been shown to exhibit potential for

Fig. 6. Uptake of parasite-derived EVs by chicken PBMC cell populations with representative flow cytometry plots. A: uptake of DiO+ EVs in monocytes. B: uptake of DiO+ EVs in thrombocytes. C: uptake of DiO+ EVs in B cells. D: uptake of DiO+ EVs in T cells. E: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of monocytes, that took up DiO+ EVs. F: *A. galli*-derived EVs stained with DiO are closely associated with the nucleus of monocytes. G: *A. galli*-derived EVs stained with DiO are closely associated with the nucleus of thrombocytes. H: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of thrombocytes, that took up DiO+ EVs. I: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of B cells, that took up DiO+ EVs. J: *A. galli*-derived EVs stained with DiO are closely associated with the nucleus of lymphocytes including B cells and T cells. K: Violin plot quantifying the percentage of T cells, that took up DiO+ EVs. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

sensing pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) through pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) such as toll-like receptors (TLRs) (Ferdous and Scott, 2023; St Paul et al., 2012). Our results show that thrombocytes may internalize EVs through mechanisms similar to phagocytosis. Lymphocytes, including both B and T cells, have also been implicated in EV-mediated communication. For example, studies have demonstrated the transfer of pathogenic protein aggregates, such as α -synuclein oligomers, between donor and recipient cells via EVs, possibly involving lymphocyte activation gene 3 (LAG3)-mediated pathways (Kwok et al., 2021). These findings suggest that EV uptake and transfer mechanisms are not restricted to innate immune cells but also extend to adaptive immune components, further supporting the plausibility of *A. galli*-derived EV interactions across a broad range of host immune cells. Notably, our study provides novel insight into the interaction between *A. galli*-derived EVs and chicken heterophils—a cell type that, to date, has not been investigated in the context of EV uptake and EV mediated cell communication. Heterophils, the avian equivalent of mammalian neutrophils, are key effector cells in

the innate immune response, functioning as a rapid first line of defense against invading pathogens (Sekelova et al., 2017). In our analysis, heterophils displayed the most pronounced uptake of EVs among the tested blood cell types, particularly in response to the female 24 h incubation-derived batch.

5. Conclusion

While *A. galli* and other chicken helminths are increasingly recognized as important pathogens, research on helminth-derived EVs and their interactions with avian host cells are limited. We successfully addressed and confirmed our initial hypotheses concerning the role of helminth EVs in early host-pathogen interaction via uptake and characteristics of *A. galli*-derived EVs. We optimized the in vitro culture of adult *A. galli* and harvesting of their EVs, providing a valuable foundation for future studies which should also comprise studies of EVs derived from *A. galli* larvae.

Investigating helminth-derived EVs in avian hosts through fundamental research—focusing on EV mediated cell communication,

uptake mechanisms, immunological responses, and host-pathogen interactions—may pave the way for developing future effective therapies.

Declarations

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

All data is available in this manuscript and its supplements.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anna Sophia Feix: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Konstantinos Papanikolaou:** Writing – review & editing. **Rikke Brødsgaard Kjærup:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Suranga Kodithuwakkku:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Alireza Fazeli:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Anders Miki Bojesen:** Conceptualization. **Carolina Corral Yélamos:** Writing – review & editing. **Tina Sørensen Dalgaard:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethics approval

The experiments involving animals were conducted according to Danish legislation governing animal experimentation (Law no. 382, 10 June 1987; Acts 739, 6 December 1988; and Act 333, 19 May 1990) and were approved by the Danish Animal Experiments Inspectorate (Animal license no. 2022-15-0201-01222).

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